

Grid-Integrated EV Charging Station with PV, Wind, and Battery Energy Storage

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KEYWORDS

EV (Electric Vehicle),
HRES
BESS
MPPT

ABSTRACT

In this research paper discusses the modeling, simulation, and performance evaluation of a Hybrid Renewable Energy System (HRES) for Electric Vehicles (EV) charging, integrating Photovoltaic (PV), wind, Battery Energy Storage System (BESS), and the utility grid. The goal is to improve reliability, efficiency, and sustainability in EV charging by leveraging renewable sources and intelligent energy management systems. MATLAB/Simulink is used to build and simulate various configurations under different irradiance, load, and storage conditions. Results show significantly improved system voltage stability, reduced grid dependency, and extended battery life when wind and PV sources are integrated with increased battery capacity. This work supports the development of self-sustaining, grid-independent EV charging infrastructure.

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing global emphasis on reducing greenhouse gas emissions and promoting sustainable energy solutions has accelerated the transition from conventional fossil fuel-based power generation to renewable energy systems. Among the renewable energy technologies, solar photovoltaic (PV) arrays and wind energy conversion systems (WECS) have gained widespread adoption due to their abundant availability, technological maturity, and declining costs. In parallel,

the rapid growth of electric vehicles (EVs) as an environmentally friendly alternative to internal combustion engine (ICE) vehicles has further intensified the demand for reliable and green electric vehicle charging infrastructure.

However, the integration of renewable energy sources with EV charging stations introduces several technical challenges. Both solar and wind energy are inherently intermittent and weather-dependent, resulting in fluctuating power outputs that do not always align with

EV charging demands. This variability can lead to instability in power supply, poor load matching, and increased stress on the utility grid. Moreover, the uncoordinated charging of large numbers of EVs can aggravate power quality issues such as voltage drops, frequency deviations, and harmonic distortions. In [1] author presents a hierarchical architecture designed to support decision-making for EV merging, trajectory regulation, and operational control. The authors reviewed an EV charging station that relies solely on power drawn from the grid[2].

Authors in [3] demonstrated the bidirectional flow of active power since grid-based EV charging demands substantial energy, an alternative energy source that is abundant and cost-effective. In this work, Author demonstrated an EV charging station powered by renewable energy sources. However, the system faces several limitations related to both load management and grid integration [4]. When PV generation is insufficient, the EV discharges power to meet grid demand a functionality known as Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G), which has been experimentally demonstrated in [5]. An online energy management strategy for a fuel cell-based hybrid multistack vehicle, utilizing game theory, has been proposed in [6]. In the paper [7] author discusses the use of a deep reinforcement learning technique with action trimming for energy management in hybrid electric vehicles powered by a fuel cell, battery, and ultracapacitor.

The integration of battery energy storage (BES) for EV charging is increasingly adopted for peak shaving. However, incorporating an additional battery raises the overall cost of the partial power processing converter, as implemented in [8]. Authors in [9] proposed a fast EV charging strategy that enables rapid energy transfer and grid support during peak hours, with battery degradation incorporated as a key objective function. The Battery-integrated charging station is demonstrated in [10] to enhance the flexibility of both the grid and electric vehicles. The system allows owners to rent or utilize charged batteries for onboard purposes. Similarly, aggregators can incorporate these batteries into virtual power plants, enabling their deployment or service provision within the smart grid framework. Authors in [11] provided a comprehensive review of EV chargers, supply equipment, and battery energy storage systems (BES). The study discusses both on-board and off-board

chargers, various converter topologies with different transformer configurations, and a range of power levels. Authors in [12] proposed an on-board charger incorporating power factor correction (PFC) implemented through a dual-active-bridge converter. An on-board charger that utilizes the grid for battery charging is presented in [13]. In paper [14] introduced a highly efficient single-stage on-board charger, which enhances overall system efficiency by eliminating an entire power conversion stage and reducing component count. This charger is primarily intended for low-power applications. In [15], the EV is charged using only the PV array and the grid. However, if both sources are unavailable, the EV battery remains uncharged. This limitation is addressed in [16], where a battery energy storage system (BES) is additionally integrated to ensure continuous charging capability. An efficient energy management system for a small-scale hybrid wind-solar-battery microgrid is proposed. It ensures power balance under varying renewable generation and load conditions using control algorithms and power converters. Real-time validation is performed through rapid control prototyping in standalone mode[17]. The design and implementation of a solar-assisted Level 2 EV charging station using a Type-1 connector, modeled in MATLAB/Simulink and validated through hardware testing is presented in [18]. Authors in [19] proposed a control strategy for a multi-port, grid-connected direct-DC PV charging station designed for plug-in electric vehicles. The system enables efficient three-way energy flow between PV modules, the grid, and vehicles, reducing conversion stages and improving flexibility. In paper [20] paper presents a DC microgrid design that uses a solar PV array and battery storage to charge electric vehicles via a single DC-DC converter with maximum power point tracking.

Integrating a wind energy source alongside the grid-connected PV array and battery energy storage system in an EV charging station offers several key advantages. This hybrid approach increases the overall penetration of clean energy, reducing dependence on the grid or fossil-fuel-based backup sources. This can lead to operational cost savings by minimizing energy purchases from the grid and reducing battery cycling, which prolongs battery life. Ultimately, the combined use of wind and solar energy contributes to significant

environmental benefits through reduced carbon emissions and a lower ecological footprint.

The main objectives of the present work are as follows:

1. The PV array and wind energy source are used together for charging the EV battery, with any surplus power being supplied to the grid and the battery energy storage (BES) system.
2. When both PV and wind sources are unavailable, the BES supplies power to charge the EV battery, minimizing power drawn from the grid and reducing its load.
3. Both the PV array and wind energy source are directly connected to the DC link in this topology, which enhances the overall system efficiency.
4. Nonlinearities in the grid are introduced because the EV charging and discharging are managed through voltage source converter (VSC) control.
5. The system demonstrates the capability for smooth and seamless synchronization between grid disconnection and reconnection operating modes.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The EV charging station integrated with battery energy storage (BES) is developed as shown in Fig. 1. The voltage source converter (VSC) manages the bidirectional flow of power among the PV array, wind energy source, BES, EV, and the grid. It converts DC power to AC and vice versa, enabling efficient power exchange with the grid. Both the EV and BES are connected to a common DC link through separate bidirectional DC-DC converters that regulate their charging and discharging operations. Interfacing inductors are installed at the point of common coupling (PCC) to mitigate harmonic currents generated by the VSC.

Fig.1. System Topology.

III. CONTROL APPROACH

The primary objective of the system is to ensure efficient charging of electric vehicles (EVs). In the absence of a grid availability, the combined power from the photovoltaic (PV) array and wind energy source is utilized to charge the battery energy storage system (BES) and EV charging station. When required, power can be discharged from the BES in the absence of a grid. The overall control strategy is divided into five major functions:

- A) Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) control for both PV and wind sources.
- B) Grid-Connected Mode Control.
- C) Synchronization and Standalone Mode Control.
- D) BESS Control.
- E) EV Control.

A) MPPT for Wind and Solar PV array:

The wind energy conversion system, a Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) strategy based on optimal torque control is implemented for a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator (PMSG). This control method calculates the reference torque using real-time measurements of wind speed and rotor/generator speed. The optimal torque is derived using the relationship

$$T_{opt} = k \cdot \omega^2 \quad (1)$$

where k is a constant determined by turbine characteristics, and ω is the generator speed. This torque reference is then tracked using Field-Oriented Control (FOC) for the PMSG, which ensures independent regulation of torque and flux by transforming three-phase currents into the dq reference frame as shown in Fig 2.

Fig.2. Wind Energy Conversion System (WECS) using a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator (PMSG).

Considering the PV side, the system uses a DC-DC converter and an MPPT control algorithm based on Perturb and Observe (P&O). The PV array generates DC power based on irradiance conditions, which are dynamically varied using a step signal that simulates an increase in solar irradiance after 0.55 seconds. The MPPT controller utilizes PV voltage and current to compute power and adjusts the converter's duty cycle to maintain operation at the maximum power point. An enable signal block controls its activation. Power and RMS blocks monitor system performance, and the converter output connects to a DC bus supplying loads like batteries, EVs, or a DC grid.

B) Grid-Connected Mode Control:

In grid-connected mode, the renewable energy system operates in coordination with the utility grid. The control strategy manages the power flow between the system (solar, wind, battery) and the grid. This regulates active and reactive power exchange to balance supply and demand, Maintains grid voltage and frequency stability by responding to changes in load or generation, and support grid reliability during fluctuations in renewable generation or load conditions. This control ensures the smooth integration of renewable sources without disturbing the overall power quality of the grid.

C) Synchronization and Standalone Mode Control:

This control strategy manages the transition between the grid-connected mode and the standalone (islanded) mode of a renewable energy system. Synchronization ensures that before connecting to the grid, the system matches the grid's voltage, frequency, and phase to prevent disturbances or damage. Standalone mode control maintains stable voltage and frequency when the system is disconnected from the grid, supplying local loads using renewable sources and battery storage. It enables a seamless and smooth transition between modes during grid faults or maintenance ensuring uninterrupted power supply and system stability.

D) BESS Control:

Manages charging/discharging cycles based on system demand and source availability in Fig 3.

Fig.3. BESS Control

The converter operates in two modes: charging (from the DC link to the battery) and discharging (from the battery to the DC link), based on logic and voltage thresholds. Specifically, a relational operator checks if the DC link voltage is greater than or equal to 400 V, and based on this condition, a selector and NOT gate enable the appropriate switches: if the voltage is ≥ 400 V, the system initiates charging mode, turning on the upper switch (boost-type operation), while if the voltage is below 400 V, the NOT gate logic enables discharging mode via the lower switch.

E) EV Control:

In Fig 4. EV battery charging/discharging with respect to user demand and system priorities. The system uses a PI controller that continuously compares the actual DC bus voltage with the reference value (48V) and generates an appropriate duty cycle to control the converter's switching devices. The core feature of this system is its ability to operate in both charging and discharging modes, depending on the voltage level of the DC bus. When the DC bus voltage is greater than or equal to 48 V, the converter enters charging mode, directing excess power to charge the battery. Conversely, when the voltage falls below 48 V, the converter switches to discharging mode, drawing power from the battery to support the DC bus.

FIG.4. EV Control

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

A) Performance of System at Outage of Grid

Fig.5a illustrates the system's simulated response during a grid outage. During the detection of the outage, the charging station switches to standalone mode (SM), causing grid voltage and current to drop to zero. The BESS compensates for the power imbalance by initiating charging, while EV charging continues without interruption.

Fig.5 a Simulated performance during grid disconnection.

B) System Performance During Grid Reconnection

Fig. 5b Simulated performance during grid reconnection.

Fig.5b shows the system's response upon grid restoration. As the grid recovers, the VSC synchronizes with it, and grid voltages and currents reappear. The BESS begins discharging, ensuring continuous EV charging without disruption.

C) Dynamic behavior of a PV-Battery-EV-Grid system under varying solar irradiance and constant EV charging load.

In Fig 6. EV charging begins with a steady current of approximately -10 A, indicating power flow into the EV from the 400 V DC bus. Initially, the battery discharges

(negative current) to support the load, with increased discharge around

0.22 s due to a supply-demand mismatch. At 0.55 s, the battery begins charging (positive current) as PV output exceeds demand, driven by irradiance rising to 950 W/m². A sharp irradiance drop to 600 W/m² at 0.58 s causes the PV current to fall to 0 A, prompting the battery to discharge again. Despite these transients, the DC bus voltage remains tightly regulated at 400 V, ensuring stable system operation.

Fig. 6. Simulated results of a PV-Battery-EV-Grid system under varying solar irradiance and constant EV charging load.

D) Performance of a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator (PMSG)-based wind energy conversion system.

Fig. 7. Waveforms depict the performance of a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator (PMSG)-based wind energy conversion system under varying wind power input.

The PMSG voltage becomes sinusoidal and balanced after 0.1 s, rising as wind power increases sharply from 0 W to 1000 W. A voltage dip occurs around 0.6 s as wind power falls to 300 W, then stabilizes after 0.75 s with power recovery. Phase currents also rise after 0.1 s, dip between 0.55–0.75 s, and remain balanced throughout. These changes confirm the PMSG's proportional

response to wind power variation and stable operation under transient conditions as demonstrated in Fig 7.

E) Power flow Dynamics of the integrated PV-BES-EV-Grid system.

Fig. 8. The power flow dynamics of the integrated PV-BES-EV-grid system.

In Fig. 8, at $t = 0$ s, PV power peaks at 7000 W, stabilizing to 3000 W at $t = 0.1$ s. It rises to 6000 W at $t = 0.2$ s and settles near 3500 W. When the grid disconnects PV drop to 0 W occurs at $t = 0.5$ s, with recovery to 2600 W after $t = 0.7$ s. EV is in continuous charging. The BESS discharges at -300 W in the absence of grid and PV. Grid power rises from 0 to 1800 W at $t = 0.08$ s, drops to 0 W at $t = 0.5$ s (disconnection), and is restored to 1800 W at $t = 0.75$ s.

F) Power flow Dynamics in a Hybrid Renewable Energy System.

The Battery Power reflects the BESS's role in power balancing. Initially, the battery absorbs a power surge (charging), evident from a sharp peak just after 0 s. It then operates near zero power until approximately 0.5 s. When the PV output drops and wind power declines, the battery starts discharging (positive power direction), supporting the load (EV Charging Station) and grid during the power shortfall. Around 0.65 s, as the PV resumes and wind power recovers, the battery reduces its output and returns near zero, indicating stabilization as depicted in Fig 9.

Fig 9. Waveforms represent power flow dynamics in a hybrid renewable energy system.

The system relies solely on PV generation, and the BESS is subjected to significant dynamic stress due to frequent fluctuations in solar power. The battery experiences rapid charge and discharge cycles, especially during grid outages, leading to higher operational strain. In contrast, both PV and wind generation, result in a more stable renewable power profile. Consequently, the BESS operates under smoother transitions with reduced power variation, minimizing stress and improving overall system efficiency. The inclusion of wind power enhances energy stability and reduces the dependency on the BESS for compensating power imbalances, thereby extending battery life and improving system reliability.

V. CONCLUSION

The simulation of the hybrid renewable energy-based EV charging system reveals that integrating wind energy and increasing battery capacity significantly enhances system performance. In the base case considering PV, BESS, and grid a step increase in irradiance from 600 W/m² to 950 W/m² at $t = 0.58$ s causes the EV charging current to rise to 25 A, with the battery and grid temporarily compensating for PV transients. The addition of wind power provides steady support, reducing battery stress and grid dependency. Enhancing the battery capacity from 300 kW to 600 kW further improves energy buffering, stabilizes the SOC, and enhances reliability under variable loads. Compared

to the base case, the hybrid system demonstrates smoother voltage and current profiles, reduced battery cycling, and near-zero grid usage, establishing it as a more efficient, stable, and self-sufficient energy solution for EV charging applications.

APPENDIX

Simulation Parameters:

$P_{pv} = 2.62$ kW, $V_{MP} = 396.15$ V, $I_{MP} = 6.636$ A; $V_{dc} = 460$ V; $V_{sab} = 223$ V, $L_f = 2$ mH;
 $S_{vsc} = 25$ kVA; $P_{wind} = 1500$ W; Wind speed = 10m/s; CB = 60 Ah; $V_B = 240$ V; $V_g = 230$ v;

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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